

IN SEARCH FOR NEW ANALEPTIC. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF *CYCLOTETRA-*METHYLENE *ISOXAZOLE*

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*cyclo*Tetramethylene *isoxazole* carboxydiethylamide has been synthesised in search for a better tolerated and a more potent analeptic.

For stimulating the respiratory and circulatory system, various analeptics, like pentamethylenetetrazole (cardiazole), diethylamide of pyridine- β -carboxylic acid (coramine), sodium camphorsulphonate amides of camphoric acid, and diethylamide of 3 : 5-dimethyl *isoxazole*-4-carboxylic acid (cycliton), pyrazine carboxylic amide, are in use. Some are good circulatory stimulant when the respiratory and circulatory mechanism is not much depressed, whereas others are better analeptic in cases of respiratory failure when there is no appreciably low blood pressure. Some are better tolerated when administered by intravenous injection and some are again more depressant than others. The analeptics are mostly heterocyclic bases with a substituted carboxamide grouping such as found in coramine (I), or cycliton (II), and/or similar compounds containing a reduced nucleus attached to a heterocyclic ring as present in pentamethylene tetrazole (cardiazole) (III), or, certain camphor derivatives.

Recent observations on the development of some analeptic activity in camphoric acid amides (D.R.P. 705652) and in various *isoxazole* carboxylic amides (B.P. 451913, 466555 and 514193) seemed to be of some special interest. The ethyl derivatives of the former have been found to exhibit the maximum respiratory and circulatory analeptic properties (Goissedet and Depois, *Compt. rend.*, 1937, 205, 1239; *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1938, v, 5, 201), and the diethylamide of 3 : 5-dimethyl-*isoxazole*-4-carboxylic acid has been noted by Reinert (*Arch. intern. pharm.*, 1937, 56, 211) to be active in stimulating the respiration. Further 3-ethyl-4-*cyclohexyl*-1 : 2 : 4-triazole has been found to exert a greater analeptic effect than cardiazole or coramine by Gronemeyer (*Chem. Abst.*, 1939, 32, 5922). We have investigated compounds which might be obtained by condensing hydroxylamine with *cyclohexanone* oxalate (IV). The *isoxazole* (V, R=Et) *via* its related acid (V, R=H) would give V(R=NEt₂).

In this paper the method of preparation of the above *isoxazole* has been fully described. In course of the isolation of the *isoxazole* acid it was noticed that the compound exists in two forms pointing thereby that the hydroxylamine had reacted with both the keto groups as present in *cyclohexanone-2-oxalate* to form two *isoxazoles* (V) and (VI) (R=Et) which had respectively given rise to 4 : 5-tetrahydrobenzo-*isoxazole-3-carboxylic acid* (V, R=H) and 3 : 4-tetrahydrobenzo-*isoxazole-5-carboxylic acid* (VI, R=H). The characteristics of the above acids as well as the pharmacological properties of their diethylamides are being studied. In order to find out whether this reaction of hydroxylamine with a diketonic carboxylate is a general one, propionyl and benzoyl acetoacetic esters have been condensed with hydroxylamine. In both cases, two isomers are isolated (*vide* experimental).

EXPERIMENTAL

Reaction of Ethyl cycloHexanone-2-oxalate with Hydroxylamine.—Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-oxalate (25 g., Kötze, *Annalen*, 1925, 342, 346) in 95% alcohol (30 c.c.) was mixed with shaking with a concentrated solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (18 g.) in water (20 c.c.). The mixture was left aside for 20 hours at room temperature. It was then diluted with water (100 c.c.) when an oil was obtained. The oil was extracted with ether; the ethereal extract was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and ether was distilled off. The ester was distilled at 120–140°/25 mm. Repeated distillation did not afford a liquid boiling within a shorter range of temperature. Total yield was 14 g.

Hydrolysis of the above Ester.—The ester (14 g.) was heated on a water-bath for 2 hours with 100 cc. sodium hydroxide solution (10%) when the whole of the ester went into solution. The solution was cooled, and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.). A white precipitate of the carboxylic acid was obtained. The acid on fractional crystallisation from water gave two crops one melting at 130° and another at 150°. Both fractions on analysis gave 8.5% nitrogen, 3 : 4-tetrahydrobenzo-*isoxazole-5-carboxylic acid* as well as 4 : 5-tetrahydrobenzo-*isoxazole-3-carboxylic acid* (C₆H₉O₃N) requires N, 8.4%.

Preparation of the Acid Chloride from the Acid (m.p. 150°).—The acid (10 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (100 c.c.), mixed with thionyl chloride (12 g.) and refluxed on a steam-bath for 48 hours. The reaction proceeded very slowly; when the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased, benzene was first distilled off and the excess of thionyl chloride was driven off under diminished pressure. The oily mass left was distilled at 95–97°/5 mm., and was obtained as a light brown oil.

Diethylamide from the above Acid Chloride.—The acid chloride (8 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (50 c.c.) and cooled thoroughly in ice. To the cooled solution was added diethylamine (8 g.) with vigorous stirring during 2 hours. After the addition was complete, the mixture was stirred for 1 hour more. The solution was then washed with ice-water, dried over potassium carbonate and concentrated under reduced pressure when a deep brown oil was left. It was distilled and collected at 160°/10 mm. It crystallised out on cooling and long standing, and melted at 49–50°. (Found : N, 12.71. C₁₂H₁₈O₂N₂ requires N, 12.6 per cent).

Diethylamide from the Acid (m.p. 130°).—The process is the same as in the above case. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed in *vacuo* and the chloride was directly used for preparing the diethylamide which was prepared as above and finally collected at 137°/10 mm. It is insoluble in water, but soluble in ordinary organic solvents. (Found: N, 12.76. $C_{12}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.6 per cent).

Ethylmethylethyl isoxazole-4-carboxylate.—Propionyl acetoacetic ester (35 g.), prepared according to the method of Bougert (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1920, I, 28) in 35 c.c. of 95% alcohol was mixed with a concentrated solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (17.5 g.) in water (20 c.c.). The mixture was left at the room temperature for 20 hours. It was then diluted with water, extracted with ether and the ether extract dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled, when ethyl ester of the *isoxazole* carboxylic acid distilled at 230–40°/755 mm.

Hydrolysis of the above Ester.—The ester (25 g.) was heated on the water-bath with sodium hydroxide solution (100 c.c., 10%) for about 1½ hours when the ester went into solution, which was cooled and slowly acidified with hydrochloric acid. At p_H 4.5, a fraction was obtained, m.p. 120–22°. On lowering the p_H further, another crop was precipitated, m.p. 102–104°. Both the fractions were separately crystallised from water. Both fractions on analysis gave N, 9.0%; 3-methyl-5-ethyl-*isoxazole-4-carboxylic* acid and 5-methyl-3-ethyl-*isoxazole-4-carboxylic* acid ($C_7H_9O_3N$) require N, 9.03%.

Acid chloride from the Acid (m.p. 120°).—The acid (1 g.) was mixed with thionyl chloride (1 g.) and refluxed on a water-bath for about 1 hour, when a clear liquid was obtained. It was distilled at 220°.

Diethylamide from the acid chloride was prepared according to the general procedure in the case of other diethylamides. It was distilled at 180°/10 mm. It is soluble in alcohol, water, ether. (Found: N, 13.4. $C_{11}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.3 per cent).

The *acid chloride from the acid* (m.p. 102°) was prepared in the usual way by the action of thionyl chloride on the dry acid. It was distilled and collected at 195°.

The *diethylamide* was prepared by the action of diethylamine on the acid chloride in ether at 0°. It was collected at 167°/8 mm. It is soluble in water, alcohol and ether. (Found: N, 13.35. $C_{11}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 13.3 per cent).

Ethylphenylmethyl isoxazole-4-carboxylate.—Benzoyl acetoacetic ester (59 g.) in 95% alcohol (150 c.c.) was mixed with a concentrated solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (44 g.) in water (45 c.c.) and the mixture was allowed to stand at the room temperature for 24 hours. It was next diluted and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with excess of sodium hydroxide solution to remove unreacted benzoylacetoacetic ester, the ether removed and the ester was distilled at 210–260°.

Hydrolysis of the Ester.—The ester (27 g.) was refluxed on a wire gauge with sodium hydroxide solution (100 c.c., 20%) for about 5 hours, when the whole of the ester went into solution. The acid was isolated in the usual manner and was fractionally crystallised from dilute alcohol (3:5). A fraction melting at 188–89° crystallised out first. The mother-liquor on further concentration gave out another crop melting at 140–42°. This latter fraction was crystallised from very dilute alcohol. Both fractions on analysis gave N, 7.0%. 3-Methyl-5-phenyl- as well as 5-methyl-3-phenyl-*isoxazole-4-carboxylic* acid require N, 6.9%.

The *acid chloride from the acid* (m.p. 188—89°) was prepared from the acid (11.5 g.) and thionyl chloride (8.8 g.). It distilled at 290°.

The *diethylamide* was prepared by treating the acid chloride (4.5 g.) in dry ether (20 c.c.) at 0° with diethylamine (1.5 g.) in dry ether (10 c.c.). The mixture was slowly treated with sodium hydroxide solution (10 c.c., 10%) and thoroughly shaken for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It was finally treated at 0° with 20 c.c. more of sodium hydroxide solution (10%). The ethereal layer was dried over solid potassium hydroxide and distilled. The diethylamide was collected at 210—15°/5 mm. It is insoluble in water, but soluble in alcohol and ether. (Found: N, 10.8. $C_{15}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.85 per cent).

The *acid chloride from the acid* (m.p. 140—42°) boils at 265°.

The *diethylamide* from this acid chloride was prepared by the usual procedure and distilled at 185—90°/5 mm. (Found: N, 10.7. $C_{15}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.8 per cent).

The physiological properties of the various diethylamides of the *isoxazole-carboxylic acids* are being studied. It is interesting to note that substitution by a phenyl group renders the compound insoluble in water.